

DATA-DRIVEN DECISION MAKING,
RESEARCH PRESENTATION
**UPGRADING
INTERNATIONAL BRANDING
OF SOFTWARE COMPANIES
TROUGH GOOGLE TRENDS'
DATA DRIVEN GOLDMINE**

research coach: Alexandra Sierra Rative

Researchers: Zita van Limpt (190665) & Sophie Kraaijeveld (201290)

Zita van Limpt
(190665)

Sophie Kraaijeveld
(201290)

OUR TEAM

TABLE OF CONTENT

- Introduction
- Literature Review
- Research Question
- Methodology
- Findings and Discussion
- Conclusions, recommendations and limitations
- Reference list
- Appendix

+

**What are we
going to talk
about?**

THE AIM OF THIS RESEARCH

Identify a problem area in Capyba's marketing goals.

Work out a quantitative research project around google trends and Capyba

Gain in-depth-knowledge on that specific topic through theories/literature review and own data collection and analysis and present this to Capyba

Describe the main idea and background

- Google Trends provides useful insights regarding online searches of specific keywords on the Google Search Engine.
- Interest, interest per regio, popular search words
- What is Branding? And why is branding important? What is B2B? What are software companies?

INTRODUCTION

Literature review

Literature Review

The main streams of literature review are followed when studying the theory related to improving the branding of a software company. The literature review includes the following streams:

1. What exactly does software mean and what is a software company.
2. business to business marketing
3. What is branding.
4. What is google trends and what insights can it give you.
5. SEM (Search engine marketing) and SEO (search engine optimization.)

RESEARCH QUESTION

HOW CAN **CAPYBA** IMPROVE THEIR
INTERNATIONAL **BRANDING** BY THE
DATA FROM **GOOGLE TRENDS**?

HOW CAN CAPYBA IMPROVE THEIR INTERNATIONAL BRANDING BY THE DATA FROM GOOGLE TRENDS?

Subquestions

- RQ1. What is the top 10 software companies worldwide that peaked in the percentage of popularity in Google Trends?
- RQ2. What is the impact on Geo-map (Google trends) based on software companies' names outside NL and NL?
- RQ3. What are topic related words that create more traffic to the B2B software companies?

METHODOLOGY

A mixed method supported by quantitative and qualitative data

+ Google Trends

On February 22, 2022, we searched for names of companies. The settings were on worldwide and for the past 12 months.

+ Google Trends

On March 25, 2022, we searched for the word Software company. The settings were on Worldwide/Netherlands/Brazil and for the past 12 months.

+ SPSS

The results of Google Trends were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). We did descriptive analysis and comparison of means (average)

+ Atlas.ti

The results of Google Trends were analyzed using Atlas.ti to form word clouds.

RESULTS

RQ1. What is the top 10 software companies worldwide that peaked in the percentage of popularity in Google Trends?

(1) Bairesdev, (2) Strv, (3) Accenture, by (4) Pridis, (5) Sofon, (6) Capyba, (7) Unleashed-technologies (8) Atomicobject (9) Vinta is and (10) Mobixtec.

RQ2. What is the impact on Geo-map (Google trends) based software companies' names outside NL and NL?

From the 24 software companies we analyzed Capyba is in number 6. We found that Capyba has a main Google search results in North and South America. Worldwide companies are global oriented.

RQ2: What is the impact on Geo-map (Google trends) based software companies' names outside NL and NL?

Dutch software companies mainly focus on the European market. Overall, there were two Dutch software companies that peaked in Google Trends. Pridis with 9,26% followed by Sofon with 7,48%

RQ3: WHAT ARE “TOPICS RELATED WORDS” THAT CREATE MORE TRAFFIC TO THE B2B SOFTWARE COMPANIES?

SEARCH WORDS IN THE NETHERLANDS

SEARCH WORDS IN BRAZIL

SEARCH WORDS WORLDWIDE

it is important for companies to use Google Trends to gain insight into words that are important to increase your search power on Google. In each country, this depends on the culture, quality concerns and potential clients.

RQ1. WHAT IS THE TOP 10 SOFTWARE COMPANIES WORLDWIDE THAT PEAKED IN THE PERCENTAGE OF POPULARITY IN GOOGLE TRENDS?

We found that Capyba has a main Google search results in North and South America. questions remain: how could Capyba expand their exposure in other continents such as Europe, Asia and Afrika. We recommend they could invest and expand in their current market by creating a global branding strategy, expand into continents they don't have impact.

RQ2. WHAT IS THE IMPACT ON GEO-MAP (GOOGLE TRENDS) BASED SOFTWARE COMPANIES' NAMES OUTSIDE NL AND NL?

Dutch software companies mainly focus on the European market. The worldwide companies are more global focused, they are more popular in Asia & North America. We found that the global companies have less impact in South America, Afrika, Oceania and Antarctica. Interesting results showed that Bairesdev, has a big impact stream of in South America compared with Capyba who only has 2,86%.

RQ3. WHAT ARE TOPICS RELATED WORDS THAT CREATE MORE TRAFFIC TO THE B2B SOFTWARE COMPANIES?

The words software, business, company, salary, testing, computing, data, customer, Warranty, home, management, and project are words that are important when searching for "software company". We assume out of our results people from the Netherlands value products that have been tested before. We also hypothesize that Brazilian software companies attend to attract business to business companies abroad.

Findings and Discussion

CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This study set out to investigate the branding of B2B software companies, and how Google Trends' data can give insight in a global branding strategy.

We found:

- Top 10 software companies worldwide and their popularity in Google Trends.
- The impact of these companies on Geo-map
- Topic related words that create more traffic to the b2b software companies.

A recommendation for Capyba is to create a global oriented branding strategy and rebranding for the dutch audience in specific. By for example have a look at the "testing part" which is really important in The Netherlands

Our limitations were: Not a lot previous research, only 24 companies and strange words like 'pizza'

Reference list

Brennan, R., Canning, L., & McDowell, R. (2020). *Business-to-Business Marketing* (Fifth ed.). SAGE Publications Ltd.

Giraldo-Romero, Y. I., Pérez-de-los-Cobos-Agüero, C., Muñoz-Leiva, F., Higuera-Castillo, E., & Liébana-Cabanillas, F. (2021). Influence of Regulatory Fit Theory on Persuasion from Google Ads: An Eye Tracking Study. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(5), 1165–1185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16050066>

Karamitros, D., Oikonomidis, T., & Fouskas, K. (2021, January 16). A Study of Digital Customer Journey through Google Trends. *ResearchGate*. Retrieved March 26, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348522989_A_Study_of_Digital_Customer_Journey_through_Google_Trends

Puhr, H. (n.d.). *Globaltrends*. *Globaltrends*. Retrieved March 14, 2022, from https://www.uibk.ac.at/smt/international-management/research/globaltrends-data/globaltrends_vignette.pdf

Probodha, J., & Vasanthapriyan, S. (2019). Analysis of Knowledge Sharing Barriers in Sri Lankan Software Companies. *International Journal of Knowledge Management*, 15(4), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijkm.2019100105>

Vaid, H. (2003). Branding defined. In H. Vaid, Ed., *Branding: Brand strategy, design and implementation of corporate and product identity* (pp. 22-45). New York: Watson-Guptill Pubns.

What is the Definition of Branding in Marketing? (n.d.). *Indeed*. Retrieved March 28, 2022, from <https://www.indeed.com/hire/c/info/definition-of-branding-in-marketing>

Xiping Song, & Osterweil, L. (1998). Engineering software design processes to guide process execution. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 24(9), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1109/32.713330>

RESEARCH POSTER

How can Capyba improve their international branding by the data from Google Trends?

A research for Capyba conducted by Zita van Limpt and Sophie Kraaijeveld.

INTRODUCTION

With the help of Google Trends we want to increase the international branding of the software company Capyba.

METHODOLOGY

Google Trends, SPSS and Atlas.ti

RESEARCH QUESTION 1

What is the top 10 software companies worldwide that peaked in the percentage of popularity in Google Trends?

We recommend they could invest and expand in their current market by creating a global branding strategy, expand into continents they don't have impact.

- (1) Bairesdev
- (2) Serc
- (3) Accenture
- (4) Pricks
- (5) Sofon
- (6) Capyba
- (7) Unleashed-technologies
- (8) Atomicobject
- (9) Vinta is and
- (10) Mobitac

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

What is the impact on Geo-map (Google trends) based software companies' names outside NL and NL?

Dutch software companies mainly focus on the European market. The worldwide companies are more global focused, they are more popular in Asia, Europe, North America. We found that the global have less impact in South America, Afrika, Oceania and Antarctica. Interesting results showed that Bairesdev, has a big impact stream of in South America compared with Capyba who only has 2,86%.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

What are topic related words that create more traffic to the B2B software companies?

The words software, business, company, salary, testing, computing, data, customer, Warranty, home, management, and project are words that are important when searching for "software company". We assume out of our results people from the Netherlands value products that have been tested before. We also hypothesize that Brazilian software companies attend to attract business to business companies abroad.

OUR POSTER

**THANK YOU FOR
LISTENING!**

DO YOU HAVE ANY QUESTIONS?